

Syntheses of 1,5-Benzothiazepines. Part-IX. Syntheses of 8-Substituted-4-(*p*-methoxyanilino)-2-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepines

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The importance of 4-methoxyphenyl moiety in biologically active compounds in 1,5-benzothiazepine class of drugs¹ prompted us to synthesise 1,5-benzothiazepines having this substituent at various positions². The present communication reports the single step syntheses of 8-substituted-4-(*p*-methoxyanilino)-2-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepines, the substituents being halogeno-fluoro, chloro, bromo; alkyl-methyl; alkoxy-methoxyl and ethoxyl (Scheme 1).

5-Substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols were reacted with substituted acetoacetanilide. Substituted benzenethiols (**1a-f**) were obtained by literature methods³ while acetoacet-4-methoxyanilide (**2**) was obtained by reacting equimolar quantities of ethyl acetoacetate and *p*-methoxyaniline under literature conditions and the melting points tallied⁴. Compounds **1a-f** were made to react with **2** in dry ethanol containing traces of gl. acetic acid to obtain **3a-f** (Scheme 1). The characterisation of **3a-f** has been carried out by elemental analyses, ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectral studies.

Results and Discussion

The occurrence of a concerted mechanism was highlighted by the fact that the characteristic ir absorption bands due to C=O and NH₂ did not appear in regions 1720-1660 and 3400-3100 cm⁻¹ respectively. On the other hand, a single band at 3300-3250 cm⁻¹ and aromatic secondary N-H bending band at 1520-1510 cm⁻¹ indicated

the presence of aromatic secondary amino group in **3a-f**. The bands, characteristic of C=N⁵ were seen at 1612-1600 cm⁻¹. In addition to the

Scheme 1

aliphatic and aromatic C-H absorptions, **3a**, **3b** and **3c** showed bands at 1215, 1150, 810 cm⁻¹; 1090, 1220 and 690 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C-F, C-Cl and C-Br respectively.

The ^1H nmr spectra of all the compounds showed the typical AA'BB' pattern of splitting of *p*-disubstituted-benzene ring, in addition to the the C-2, CH₃ singlet at δ 1.88–2.26, a broad singlet C-4, NH-aryl signal at δ 8.20–8.40 and C-4', –OCH₃, 3H singlet at δ 3.48–3.60. The well-resolved spectra of **3d**, **3e** and **3f** showed the signals at δ 6.50–6.66 (1H, dd, *J* 8 Hz *o*-coupled, *J* 0.5 Hz *p*-coupled), C-6, –H), 6.40–6.56 (1H, dd, *J* 8 Hz, *o*-coupled, *J* 3 Hz *m*-coupled, C-7, –H) and 6.16–6.28 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz *m*-coupled, C-9, –H). **3d** gave a singlet corresponding to three protons at δ 2.20. Signals at δ 3.72 (3H, s) in **3e** and δ 1.24 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz) and 3.84 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz) in **3f** corresponded to the presence of OCH₃ and OCH₂CH₃ in the respective compounds. Besides, δ 7.08–7.28 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C-2', –H and C-6', –H) and 6.98–7.04 (2H, d, *J* 7 Hz, C-3', –H and C-5', –H) were also distinguished (Table 1). A 1H singlet at δ 6.10–6.30 may be assigned to C-3, –H.

The mass spectrum of **3c** showed a cluster of three peaks at *m/z* 374 [*M*⁺], 376 [*M* + 2]⁺ and 378 [*M* + 4]⁺ indicating the presence of bromine.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-577

spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) at 60 MHz or Jeol-90 MHz F.T. nmr instrument with TMS as internal standard. Pyridine:alcohol (3:2) was used as solvent system in tlc on silica gel G coated glass plates for ascertaining the purity of the products. Elemental analyses results were within the permissible limits of error (0.5%).

Acetoacet-4-methoxyanilide (**2**): A mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (13.0 g, 0.1 mol) and 4-methoxyaniline (12.3 g, 0.1 mol) was refluxed on an oil-bath (130–40°) for 8 h. On cooling, the dark greenish mixture, a solid that separated out was washed with ether and crystallised from boiling water as colourless plates (13.4 g, 65%), m.p. 116° (lit.⁴ 117–18°).

8-Methoxy-4-(p-methoxyanilino)-2-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepine (**3e**): The reaction mixture of 2-amino-5-methoxybenzenethiol (**1a**; 0.155 g, 0.001 mol), acetoacet-4-methoxyanilide (**2**; 0.20 g, 0.001 mol), dry ethanol (10 ml) and glacial acetic acid (1 ml) was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath. On cooling and removing the excess solvent from the reaction mixture, a brown residue was obtained which was crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals (0.13 g, 40%), m.p., 182°, *R*_f 0.69 (Found: C, 66.12; H, 5.39. C₁₈H₁₈SN₂O₂ requires: C, 66.25; H, 5.52%); ν_{max} 3345 (NH) and 1612

TABLE 1— ^1H NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Compd. no.	C-2,CH ₃	C-3,H	C-4,N-H	C-4',OCH ₃	C-8,X	Aromatic protons				
						C-6,H	C-7,H	C-9,H	C-2',H C-6',H	C-3',H C-5',H
3a	2.20 (3H, s)	6.18 (s)	8.26 (b)	3.62 (3H, s)	–	–	6.40–7.32 (7H, m)	–	–	–
b	2.24 (3H, s)	6.24 (s)	8.28 (b)	3.68 (3H, s)	–	–	6.24–7.28 (7H, m)	–	–	–
c	2.16 (3H, s)	6.10 (s)	8.32 (b)	3.60 (3H, s)	–	–	6.44–7.38 (7H, m)	–	–	–
d	1.92 (3H, s)	6.28 (s)	8.40 (b)	3.76 (3H, s)	2.20 (3H, s)	6.54 (dd, <i>J</i> , 0.5)	6.52 (dd, <i>J</i> , 8, 3)	6.24 (d, <i>J</i> 3)	7.28 (2H, d, <i>J</i>)	7.04 (2H, d, <i>J</i>)
f	1.88 (3H, s)	6.16 (s)	8.24 (b)	3.64 (3H, S)	1.24 (t, 3H, 7) 3.84 (d, 2H, <i>J</i>)	6.66 (dd, <i>J</i> , 0.5)	6.56 (dd, <i>J</i> , 3)	6.24 (d, <i>J</i> 3)	7.20 (2H, d, <i>J</i>)	7.00 (2H, d, <i>J</i>)

**J* in Hz.

NOTE

cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 2.20 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.12 (1H, s, C-3, -H), 8.28 (1H, b, N-H), 3.72 (3H, s) and 3.60 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.62 [1H, (dd, J 8 Hz (o -coupling), 0.5 Hz (p -coupling), C₆, -H], 6.44 [1H, (dd, J 8, 3 Hz (o - and m -coupled), C-7, -H], 6.26 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, C-9, -H), 7.08 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, C-2', -H and C-6', -H), 6.98 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, C-3', -H and C-5', -H); M^+ 326, $[\text{M} + 2]^+$ 328 (4% of M^+).

3a-d and **3f** were similarly prepared (yields 30–45%) : **3a**, m.p. 220°, R_f 0.71; **b**, 226°, 0.65; **c**, 160°, 0.66; **d**, 230°, 0.72; **f** 190°, 0.72.

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